

Multiphase PtPdSb nanoparticles for direct electrochemical energy conversion using hydrogen-rich dimethyl ether

Medhanie Gebremedhin Gebru^a, Itay Pitussi^a, Hanan Teller^a, Achyuth Marammuri Chathoth^a, Haya Kornweitz^a, Rostislav Medlín^b, Petr Bělský^b, Palaniappan Subramanian^{b,*}, Alex Schechter^{a,b,*}

^a Department of Chemical Science, Ariel University, Ariel, 40700, Israel

^b Research and Development Centre for Renewable Energy, New Technologies Research Centre (NTC), University of West Bohemia, Univerzitni, 8/2732 301 00, Pilsen, Czech Republic

HIGHLIGHTS

- A novel Genkenite phase PtPdSb catalyst for DME electrooxidation.
- Low PGM loading gives a highest specific power density of 150 mW mg_{PGM}⁻¹ for DDMEFC.
- Explored a possible DME oxidation reaction pathway on the PtPdSb catalyst.

ABSTRACT

Dimethyl ether (DME) is a promising next-generation renewable fuel for polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells (PEMFC) because of its high energy density, ease of handling and supply, nontoxicity, reduced crossover, and ability to be obtained from a wide range of renewable sources. However, its commercialization has not yet been realized, owing to the low activity of state-of-the-art catalysts. We have synthesized a novel Genkenite ternary metal catalyst, Pt_xPd_ySb_z/C, with varying metal compositions and tested its activity towards DME oxidation in both three-electrode flooded cell and in single fuel cell configurations. Some important insights into the DME reaction mechanism were gleaned using *ex-situ* Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and were supported by density functional theory (DFT) computations. A direct DME fuel cell constructed with 1.2 and 3.1 mg_{PGM} cm⁻² loading of Pt₅PdSb₄/C and Pt/C as anode and cathode catalysts, respectively, operating at 65 °C temperature and no back pressure delivered a peak power density of 180 mW cm⁻² and one of the highest reported current density of 360 mA cm⁻² at 0.5 V. Moreover, the catalyst provided the highest PGM (Pt+Pd) mass normalized power density of 150 mW mg_{PGM}⁻¹.

1. Introduction

Gaseous hydrogen has been the preferred fuel choice for operating proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) because of its ease of oxidation and the generation of environmentally friendly water as the only product. However, currently, a major portion of hydrogen is generated from fossil fuel reforming, resulting in carbon emissions [1]. Furthermore, hydrogen lacks efficient storage, transport, and delivery [2]. Numerous studies have been conducted on the use of small organic molecules (methanol, ethanol, and formic acid) as alternative liquid fuels for power generation using PEMFC technology [3–5]. Table 1 compares different fuels explored for PEMFCs. Dimethyl ether (DME), one of the promising circular hydrogen carriers, is considered a potential

fuel for PEMFCs owing to its several advantages over alternative liquid fuels [6].

DME is the simplest ether molecule that can be derived directly from natural gas reforming or indirectly from the dehydration of methanol produced from syngas or the hydrogenation of CO₂ [12]. DME is a reliable energy carrier for use in diesel engines without releasing pollutants (SO_x and NO_x) owing to its low combustion noise and fast evaporation [12]. It can be liquefied at -25 °C under atmospheric pressure or room temperature under 5–6 bar thus allowing the utilization of transport tankers and existing supply infrastructure built for liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) for its delivery. The complete electrooxidation of DME involves the exchange of 12 electrons as shown in equations (1)–(3), which is higher than that of methanol (6 electrons)

* Corresponding author. Department of Chemical Science, Ariel University, Ariel, 40700, Israel.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: palans@ntc.zcu.cz (P. Subramanian), salex@ariel.ac.il (A. Schechter).

[13]. Because of its lower dipole moment (1.30 D), DME has a lower crossover through the Nafion membrane than methanol [14]. This is evident from the crossover current density values of 35 and 1.5 mA cm⁻² reported for methanol and dimethyl ether-operated fuel cells, respectively, employing a Nafion 211 membrane [6,15]. At ambient temperature, the direct DME fuel cell (DDMEFC) has nearly the same open circuit potential (1.18 V) as the direct methanol and ethanol fuel cells (1.21 and 1.15 V) [16]. Unlike ethanol, DME electrooxidation does not proceed via C-C bond cleavage, making its electrooxidation kinetically facile [16].

Similar to other hydrocarbons, the oxidation of DME on a single and polycrystalline Pt leads to surface poisoning by reaction intermediates such as CO [17]. Alloying Pt with oxophilic metals such as Ru, Sn, Ag, Mo, Cr, Ni, Co, W, and Cu has been investigated exhibiting an increased oxidation current of hydrocarbon fuels and improved tolerance to poisonous intermediates [18–20]. These metals can alter the electronic properties of Pt to decrease the binding energy of CO_{ads} to the Pt surface (electronic ligand effect) or provide oxide species from water activation at a lower potential than Pt to oxidize and remove CO_{ads} as CO₂ (bifunctional mechanism) [21]. The contribution of oxophilic metals to the activity enhancement of Pt or PtPd catalysts towards DME oxidation has been investigated in previous reports [16,22–24]. A strong time/potential-dependent dynamics experienced during the operation of direct hydrocarbon fuel cell has been identified as a key difference contributing to the lower power output compared to those using other fuels such as hydrogen [25]. Furthermore, poor water-DME miscibility has been attributed to the lower power output measured by operating liquid-fed direct DME fuel cells [26].

Alloying Sb with precious metals (Pt and Pd) has been proven to improve the electrocatalytic properties and alleviate the intermediate poisoning of noble metals during the electrooxidation of hydrocarbons. PtSb/PdSb-based electrocatalytic materials have been reported to oxidize C1 molecules such as methanol [27], formic acid, and CO_{ads} [28, 29] as well as C2 molecules including ethanol [30]. Interestingly, DME electrooxidation on antimony-based catalysts has not been investigated, despite the above-mentioned properties.

Motivated by the ongoing need for the development of a new and more active electrocatalyst for DME oxidation and considering the aforementioned advantages of Sb, we prepared and explored the catalytic activity of ternary metal catalysts alloyed with Sb for DME oxidation. Ternary metal catalysts containing Pt, Pd, and Sb with different metal compositions, supported on Vulcan XC72 (Pt_xPd_ySb_z/C), were synthesized using an ethylene glycol-assisted thermal reduction method. Detailed physico-chemical characterization of the catalysts was performed by X-ray diffraction, small-angle X-ray scattering, high-resolution transmission electron microscopy, scanning transmission electron microscopy, and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. The activity of these catalysts toward DME electrooxidation was studied in an aqueous solution in a conventional three-electrode cell and as a DME-fed gas at low temperature in a 4 cm² single membrane electrode assembly

(MEA) fuel cell. The products of the DME electrochemical oxidation reaction during fuel cell operation were analyzed using *ex-situ* Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). The spectroscopic data analysis combined with theoretical computation performed using first principle calculations resulted in the proposal of a DME electrochemical oxidation reaction pathway for the Sb-based ternary alloy catalysts as described in the following sections of this article.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Potassium tetrachloroplatinate (K₂PtCl₄) (99.9 %) and palladium (II) chloride (PdCl₂) (99.9 %) were purchased from STREM and Ethylene glycol (99.5 %), H₂SO₄ (95–97 %), NaOH (99.9 %), and antimony (III) chloride (SbCl₃) (99.0 %) were purchased from Merck. DME (99.9 %) gas tank with 10 L capacity and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) (60 wt % dispersion in H₂O) were procured from Sigma Aldrich. Nafion® solution (5 wt % in a mixture of lower aliphatic alcohols and water) and teflonized carbon cloth (LT1400W, ELAT® GDL microporous layer) were supplied from IonPower and E-Tek DivisionSM, respectively. Nafion membranes and Toray carbon paper (TGP H090) were obtained from FuelCellStore. Isopropyl alcohol was obtained from DAEJUNG chemicals. Distilled water with a conductivity of 18.2 MΩ was used throughout the experiment.

2.2. Pt_xPd_ySb_z/C catalysts synthesis

The catalysts were prepared using a modified ethylene glycol-assisted thermal reduction method reported previously [31]. The required mass of each of the three precursor salts (K₂PtCl₄, PdCl₂, and SbCl₃) needed to prepare the Pt_xPd_ySb_z/C catalyst with a given stoichiometry was separately dissolved in ethylene glycol (EG) (4 mg of metal salt per 1 mL EG) by vigorous stirring. The solution was mixed and stirred for 1 h. Concentrated NaOH solution was added until the pH of the solution reached 12–13. The solution was then heated to 100 °C for 1 h and refluxed at 180 °C for 2 h. Following this step, EG-dispersed Vulcan XC72 carbon (30 wt % of the total metal weight) was added, and the solution was stirred overnight. The precipitate was separated from the solution, washed with a mixture of water and acetone several times using centrifugation-solvent removal cycles, and oven-dried at 70 °C overnight.

2.3. Physico-chemical characterization

A detailed physico-chemical characterization was performed on the selected Pt_xPd_ySb_z/C composition, Pt₅PdSb₄/C, chosen for its superior performance in DME electrooxidation in the three-electrode cell. Elemental analysis was conducted using inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) (Thermo iCAP 6300 Duo, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) (AZtec, Oxford Instruments) to confirm the stoichiometric ratio of each metal in the prepared catalysts. The available phases and crystal structures were analyzed using X-ray diffractometry (XRD) (SmartLab, Rigaku) with a Cu Kα radiation source (λ = 1.54 Å). A detailed analysis

Table 1
Comparison of physical properties of common fuels of PEMFC [7–11].

Properties	H ₂	Methanol	Ethanol	Formic acid	Ammonia	DME
Boiling point (°C)	–252.9	64.7	78.32	108	–33.34	–24
Energy density (kWh kg ⁻¹)	38.88	6.10	8.00	1.77	4.00	8.20
Toxicity (oral LD ₅₀) (mg kg ⁻¹)	500–5000	5628	60000	730	350	82000
Dipole moment (D)	0	1.70	1.69	1.40	1.47	1.30
Theoretical E _{oc} (V)	1.20	1.21	1.15	1.48	1.17	1.17

of the diffraction peaks was conducted by comparing them with the database uploaded to X'pert HighScore Plus software (Version 3.0). Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) (SmartLab, Rigaku and SAXSess mc², Anton Paar) was used to determine the particle size distribution (PSD). The nanocatalyst samples were measured in the form of powder glued between two pieces of scotch tape. The Irena software package was used for SAXS data processing and evaluation (modeling) [32]. The log-normal volume-weighted particle size distribution (PSD) was applied in the Modeling tool of the Irena software to model the SAXS profiles. Particle shapes and their PSD were further confirmed by high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (JEM 2200FS, JEOL) operated at 200 kV with CCD Gatan (Digital Micrograph software) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) (MAIA3 Triglav™, Tescan). STEM-EDS measurements were performed using a Jeol JSM 2200FS instrument in STEM mode operated at 200 kV with a convergence angle of 20.0 mrad. The probe current was adjusted to ~85 pA. The microscope was equipped with an Oxford Instruments X-Max EDS detector with 80 mm² active area. The EDS elemental concentrations were calculated in the Inca SW (Oxford Instruments) using the standard Cliff-Lorimer (K-factor) quantification method. STEM-EDS chemical maps were produced by integrating the intensity at the Pd (La), Pt (La), and Sb (La) absorption peaks ROI, respectively. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was carried out on a Thermo Scientific Nexsa spectrometer with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source ($h\nu \sim 1.5$ keV) in an ultra-high vacuum chamber (10^{-10} - 10^{-9} Torr).

2.4. Electrochemical measurements

The electrochemical measurements were conducted in a conventional three-electrode cell containing 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte saturated with either N₂ or DME gases controlled using a VSP Bio-Logic Electrochemical workstation. A graphite rod and Ag/AgCl (Metrohm, 3 M KCl) electrodes were used as the counter and reference electrodes, respectively. The distance between the three electrodes was maintained at 1 cm throughout the electrochemical measurements in aqueous solutions. All measured potentials were converted to and expressed in terms of the normal hydrogen electrode (NHE) unless specifically mentioned otherwise. The working electrode was prepared by drop-casting a 4 μ L aliquot from a catalyst ink on glassy carbon (GC) with a cross-sectional area of 0.196 cm² which resulted in a catalyst loading (mass of the metals + carbon support) of 50 μ g cm⁻². To prepare the catalyst ink, 4 mg of Pt_xPd_ySb_z/C catalyst powder and 18 μ L of Nafion solution (20 wt% of the catalyst powder) were dispersed in 1.6 mL of a 1:1 mixture of distilled water and isopropyl alcohol. Surface cleaning and catalyst activation were performed by cycling the cell in the potential range of 0.05–1.1 V at a scan rate of 100 and then 10 mV s⁻¹ in an N₂-saturated solution until a stable voltammogram was obtained. Cyclic voltammetry (CV), chronoamperometry (CA), and linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurements were performed after saturating the solution with DME (0.74 M at room temperature) and maintaining a gas blanket above the solution throughout the experiment or pre-adsorbing CO (99.9 %) on the working electrode. Potentiodynamic stripping of pre-adsorbed CO was performed following the procedure described in our previous paper [33]. In short, the 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte solution was saturated with CO, and a chronoamperogram was recorded at 0.05 V for 1 min to adsorb CO on the catalyst surface. Subsequently, excess CO present in the solution was removed by purging the solution with N₂. The pre-adsorbed CO was then oxidized by cycling the electrode between the CO adsorption potential and the potential at which the adsorbed CO was fully oxidized (0.05–1.1 V).

2.5. Preparation of catalyst-coated membrane and fuel cell testing

The preparation of the catalyst ink to be sprayed on Nafion membrane 212 (thickness of ~50 μ m) is similar to that described above, with the addition of 10 wt% PTFE to the catalyst ink for wet proofing. The

catalyst-coated membrane (CCM) was prepared by spraying the Pt₅PdSb₄/C ink (selected composition based on the performance in the three-electrode cell) on the anode and Pt/C ink on the cathode sides of a 4 cm² area cleaned membrane held on a hot vacuum plate (70 °C) using a spray coater system (SimCoat, Sono-Tek). Direct spraying on the membrane avoids the need for hot pressing and provides better membrane-catalyst contact. The platinum group metal (PGM) loading on the anode and cathode sides were 1.2 and 3.1 mg_{PGM}⁻¹ cm⁻², respectively. The CCM was then sandwiched between two graphite bipolar plates of a fuel cell (Scribner Associates Inc.) with an active electrode area of 4 cm² backed with Toray paper and Teflonized carbon cloth on the anode and cathode sides, respectively, serving as gas diffusion layers.

The assembled cell was operated using a Scribner fuel cell testing system (850g, Scribner Associates Inc.). DME and compressed air flowing at 40 and 300 mL min⁻¹ passed through the anode and cathode humidifier bottles of the system, respectively, and were supplied to the fuel cell. The temperature of the fuel cell and humidifier bottles was maintained at 65 °C to ensure 100 % relative humidity of the reactant gases, which corresponds to a water concentration of 0.159 g L⁻¹. The cell was initially conditioned by maintaining the potential at 0.2 V for 20 min and the open circuit potential (E_{OC}) was stabilized by flowing gases for an additional 30 min. Finally, the polarization curve was measured in the range of E_{OC} - 0.05 V at 0.02 V step with each step held for 10 s.

2.6. Ex-situ FTIR study of DME oxidation mechanism

The DME oxidation mechanism of the selected catalyst was studied by analyzing the DME oxidation products using ex-situ Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy (Vertex 70, Bruker) as shown in the experimental setup in Fig. S1. A fuel cell was operated in a half-cell configuration (DME-saturated 0.5 M H₂SO₄ was circulating through the anode from a vial at 15 mL min⁻¹ using a peristaltic pump and humidified H₂ gas through the cathode at 40 mL min⁻¹). Half-cell configuration enables the separation of anode and cathode processes in working fuel cell systems and has been used to study the effects of CO poisoning and fuel cell voltage oscillations. The cathode with humidified H₂ gas acts as a dynamic reference electrode and has been used for the determination of single electrode potential versus current density curves directly in the fuel cell during operation, enabling distinct determination of single electrode performance [34–36]. A 0–1.2 V (vs. H₂/Pt cathode electrode) at an interval of 0.2 V was applied on the Pt₅PdSb₄/C-coated anode electrode for 2 h at each potential. The products released from the anode outlet were returned to the vial to collect most of the DME oxidation products. A sample taken from the vial was then dropped onto a platinum ATR accessory of the FTIR spectrometer, and the spectra were recorded. DME-saturated 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution was used as the background.

2.7. DFT calculations

The Vienna ab initio simulation program (VASP) was used to calculate periodic boundary conditions [37,38]. The electron-ion interactions were described using the projected augmented wave (PAW) method [39], and the semi-local exchange-correlation functional employed the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) of Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE) [40,41]. Reproducible results were obtained with a cut-off energy of 500 eV and a 5 × 5 × 1 Monkhorst k-point mesh for Brillouin zone sampling [42]. For geometry relaxation, the convergence criteria were set to 1 × 10⁻⁴ eV for the total energy and 1 × 10⁻⁴ eV Å⁻¹ for the forces, with ion positions, relaxed while the cell volume and shape remained constant. All calculations included van der Waals (VDW) corrections using the DFT-D2 approach proposed by Grimme [43] and implemented in the VASP by Bučko [44]. The solvent effects were evaluated using VaspSol [45], and the Gibbs free energy values

incorporated zero-point energy (ZPE) corrections.

Calculations were performed for the surface of Pt₅PdSb₄. This structure was constructed by modifying a known Pd₃Te₂ structure [46]. Two bulk unit cells were used to achieve a ratio of 6:4 for M:Sb (M = Pt or Pd); five Pd atoms were replaced with Pt atoms, and Te atoms were replaced with Sb atoms. Six potential structures (structures C1 - C6) resulting from this modification were considered, and their structures and energies are given in Table S1. Structure C3 was chosen for this study because it has the lowest free energy. The calculated slab comprised 25 Pt atoms, 5 Pd atoms, and 20 Sb atoms, with a 16 Å vacuum layer separating the slabs. Calculations were performed on the Pt₅PdSb₄ (314) surface according to the highest peak observed in the XRD measurements. The supercell slab was constructed using the AFLOW software [47] and had a surface area of 180.03 Å². Equation (4) defines the adsorption energy E_{ads} of a particle on a metallic slab.

$$E_{ads} = E_{particle^*} - E^* - E_{particle} \quad (4)$$

Where $particle^*$ represents the adsorbed particle, $E_{particle^*}$ is the total energy of the adsorbed particle, E^* is the total energy of the metallic slab, and $E_{particle}$ is the total energy of the particles in the aqueous phase. Equation (5) was used to calculate the reaction energy.

$$\Delta G_{reaction} = \sum (\Delta E_{ads})_{products} + \sum (\Delta G_{reaction})_{aq} - \sum (\Delta E_{ads})_{reactants} \quad (5)$$

Here, $\Delta G_{reaction}$ represents the energy change associated with the elemental reaction over an alloy. The sum of the E_{ads} of all the products and reactants is represented by $\sum (\Delta E_{ads})_{products}$ and $\sum (\Delta E_{ads})_{reactants}$, respectively. The energy change associated with the elementary reaction step in the aqueous phase was represented by $\sum (\Delta G_{reaction})_{aq}$. When a potential U is applied, the free energy of the electrons is shifted by $|e|U$, where $|e|$ is the absolute charge of the electron. This shift is only applied to redox reactions that release H^+ and e^- not to potential-independent reactions in which homolytic bond cleavage is performed.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Electrochemical measurements

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements in N₂ and DME-saturated 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solutions in a three-electrode cell using Pt_xPd_ySb_z/C-based ternary metal catalysts with different x: y: z atomic ratios are displayed in Fig. S2, and the electrochemical parameters based on this figure are summarized in Table S2.

The hydrogen under potential desorption (H_{UPD}) in the potential region of 0.05–0.35 V and the oxide formation/reduction at 0.6–1.1 V are detected in all the catalysts. The electrochemical surface area (ECSA) was calculated from the average charge (Q_A) obtained by integrating the H_{UPD} region, excluding the contribution of the double-layer region using Equation (6).

$$ECSA = \frac{Q_A}{Q_H L_{PGM}} \quad (6)$$

Where L_{PGM} is the platinum group metal (PGM) content present in the catalyst and Q_H is the average charge of hydrogen adsorption on Pt and Pd, assumed to be 2.1×10^{-5} mC m⁻² [6]. An increase in the ECSA of the catalyst resulted in a greater number of available active sites for hydrogen adsorption. Nonetheless, the hydrogen and DME active sites aren't identical. Despite having the highest ECSA among the tested catalysts (~ 51 m² g_{PGM}⁻¹), Pt₃PdSb₆/C did not exhibit the highest DME oxidation current. A catalyst containing a higher Pt content than Pd presented a larger ECSA (Table S2). This observation suggests that the Pd site strongly interacts with Sb, which weakens the Pd-H bond [48]. This was supported by the voltammograms recorded in the N₂-saturated electrolyte shown in Fig. S3. Pd/C showed two peaks were observed at lower (0.12 V) and higher (0.27 V) potentials within the hydrogen

underpotential (H_{UPD}) region. These peaks correspond to the adsorption of the β and α phase hydrogen, respectively [49]. The peaks observed in the reverse scan are assigned to the adsorption of hydrogen. Pure Palladium is known to exhibit a high affinity for hydrogen and possesses a greater number of hydrogen adsorption sites. However, alloying Pd with antimony (Sb) alters the binding energy of hydrogen on the Pd surface, resulting in a weaker hydrogen binding [50]. Consequently, the Pd/C catalyst exhibits higher currents as compared to the binary catalyst PdSb/C. In comparison to Pd/C, the PtSb/C exhibited a suppressed H_{UPD} behavior with the calculated ECSA reduced from 63.8 m² g_{PGM}⁻¹ for Pd/C to 11.2 m² g_{PGM}⁻¹ for PtSb/C. The incorporation of Sb into the Pd lattice withdraws electrons from the Pd, lowering the electron density around Pd atoms and the electronic structure of Pd. Additionally, Sb can cause changes in lattice strain due to the difference in atomic radii between Pd and Sb, which modifies the surface geometry and Pd-Pd bond distances [51]. These electronic and strain changes typically alter the adsorption sites and energies, leading to shifts in the hydrogen adsorption/desorption peaks (Fig. S3).

In the presence of DME in the electrolyte, the H_{UPD} region of the CVs recorded by all catalysts exhibited some current suppression (Fig. S2). We attributed this suppression to the adsorption of DME at low potentials below 0.3 V which competes with the hydrogen of hydronium (H_3O^+) from the electrolyte adsorption on the same Pt active sites [24]. As seen in Fig. S2, the higher the DME oxidation peak current density provided by the catalyst, the larger the differences between the currents and charges recorded in the DME-saturated solutions and the supporting electrolyte in the H_{UPD} region. This result suggests that the higher current provided by the catalyst is ascribed to higher DME adsorption. Among the catalysts, Pt₅PdSb₄/C exhibited the highest PGM (Pt + Pd)-normalized anodic peak current density of 52.95 ± 2.30 mA mg_{PGM}⁻¹ seen in Fig. 1a (the DME oxidation region in the potential range 0.6–1 V is overlaid for clarity). Compared to the N₂-saturated solution, Pt₅PdSb₄/C demonstrated a 25 % decrease in ECSA (Fig. S4). In contrast, the catalyst with the lowest peak power density of 1.05 ± 0.32 mA mg_{PGM}⁻¹, Pt₂Pd₄Sb₄/C, experienced only a minor 3.5 % ECSA loss under the same conditions. Pt₅PdSb₄/C also depicted the highest oxidation charge of 170.82 ± 4.18 mC mg_{PGM}⁻¹ calculated from the area under the curve in the DME oxidation region and the lowest oxidation onset potential of 0.58 V.

No significant differences were observed in the DME oxidation peak potentials of the catalysts, which appeared at approximately 0.8 V. The 3D surface plot in Fig. 2 shows that the oxidation charge increases with increasing Pt and decreasing Pd content at a constant Sb content of 40 %. Nonetheless, the absence of Pd led to lower activity in DME oxidation, as observed in the cyclic voltammetry of Pt₅PdSb₄/C and PtSb/C, which displayed peak current densities of 52 and 37 mA mg_{PGM}⁻¹, respectively, at 0.8 V (Fig. S5). Some explanation can be found in Dumont et al. work who performed DFT calculations of DME oxidation on PtPdRu and found that the Pd improved the DME oxidation kinetics of PtRu sites by increasing the DME binding energy and decreasing the activation energy of C-O and C-H bonds scission of adsorbed DME [52]. They also reported that the promotive role of Pd was achieved by limiting the Pd content to approximately 10 %. Similarly, in our study, Sb-based ternary catalysts with only 10 % Pd (Pt₅PdSb₄/C) exhibited superior performance in terms of both peak current density and DME oxidation charge.

The anodic currents observed during the reverse direction potential are lower than in the forward scan (Fig. 1b). This difference is attributed to the limited number of active sites for DME adsorption due to unreduced oxygen species and CHO intermediates such as $-CH_3O_{ads}$, $-CH_2O_{ads}$, and $-CH_3_{ads}$, as suggested by the DFT, formed in the anodic scan. Hence, the currents seen in the reverse scan (peak III) represent the reaction balance between the anodic removal of these intermediates at potentials lower than 0.85 V limited by reaction surface kinetics and not by the potential, as evident from the flattening of the current in the extended region of 0.7 V down to 0.3 V. Interestingly, the observed anodic currents even within the potential region of H_{UPD} (below 0.3 V)

Fig. 1. (a) CV recorded in a DME-saturated 0.5 M H₂SO₄ using Pt_xPd_ySb_z/C catalysts (b) CV recorded in N₂ and DME-saturated 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution using Pt₅PdSb₄/C. (c) Background-corrected CO stripping of different catalysts. (d) Onset potential and oxidation charge of CO stripping for the catalysts. (e) I vs. t plot corresponding to DME oxidation at 0.8 V on Pt₅PdSb₄/C. (50 μg cm⁻² catalyst loading and 10 mV s⁻¹ scan rate, unstirred solution).

Fig. 2. A 3D plot of the metal% vs. DME oxidation charge. (50 μg cm⁻² catalyst loading and 10 mV s⁻¹ scan rate).

in the reverse scan suggests that some of the surface's sites are still covered by reactive CHO intermediates formed at high potentials in the forward scan. Such activity in this potential region has been seen in formic acid and methyl formate oxidation. Anodic currents within the H_{UPD} region are not seen in the case of other anodic reactions of other small organic molecules such as methanol. Pt₅PdSb₄/C and Pt₄Pd₂Sb₄/C showed clearly resolved doublet oxidation peaks appearing at around 0.74 and 0.81 V (Peak I and II in Fig. 1b). Electrochemical measurements performed in a DME-saturated HClO₄ electrolyte, however, showed a single anodic peak rather than overlapping peaks [23,53], suggesting that the doublet peak observed using DME-saturated 0.5 M H₂SO₄ might be attributed to the adsorption of sulfate species.

Generally, the electrooxidation of most small organic molecules on Pt-containing catalysts generates strongly adsorbed Pt-CO as an intermediate leading to poisoning [54,55]. To examine the effect and the contribution of each metal to CO removal, potentiodynamic stripping of pre-adsorbed CO was performed, as described in the experimental section.

Fig. 1c shows the CO stripping experiment performed using the most electroactive catalyst, Pt₅PdSb₄/C, and other selected control catalysts. Pt₅PdSb₄/C and PtSb/C showed broader CO oxidation potential regions

than the catalysts without Sb (Pt/C and PtPd/C). Pt₅PdSb₄/C showed slightly higher CO oxidation onset potential than PtSb/C (0.44 vs. 0.42 V). Oxidation of pre-adsorbed CO on Pt/C started at 0.7 V. The onset of the pre-adsorbed CO oxidation on Pt/C occurred at 0.7 V. In contrast, both PtPd/C and PtSb/C displayed CO oxidation onset potentials lower by 0.22 V and 0.3 V respectively, compared to Pt/C. However, Pt₅PdSb₄/C demonstrated significantly more intense CO oxidation peak current and charge values (24 mA mg_{PGM}⁻¹ and 101.5 mC mg_{PGM}⁻¹) in comparison to PtSb/C (10 mA mg_{PGM}⁻¹ and 38 mC mg_{PGM}⁻¹), as illustrated in Fig. 1d. This observation suggests that the presence of both Pd and Sb improved the CO removal ability of Pt, as depicted in (Fig. 1d) with the effect of Sb being particularly pronounced. As seen in Fig. 1c, a small current attributed to the CO removal in the formate (HCOO⁻) route [56] is seen in the broad peak from 0.3 to 0.6 V in PtSb and Pt₅PdSb₄ voltammograms, which is completely absent in the Pt electrode voltammogram.

Kashyap et al. [23] reported that Pd overcomes CO poisoning of Pt by increasing the adsorption energy of CO on the Pt surface and weakening its binding energy. However, Sb overcomes the CO poisoning of Pt in a manner similar to other reported oxophilic metals, such as Sn and Ru, through ligand effects and bifunctional mechanisms. In the ligand effect, the second metal alters the electronic properties of Pt due to the difference in electronegativity, resulting in the weakening of the Pt-CO interaction. In the bifunctional mechanism, the second metal can promote the oxidation of CO via the formation of oxygen species (OH) by activating water at a lower potential than Pt alone. The comparatively lower CO oxidation onset potential observed on PtSb/C compared to PtPd/C is attributed to the more oxophilic nature of antimony than palladium. The XPS spectra of the metals revealed that most of the Sb was present in the Sb³⁺ (Sb₂O₃) oxidation state. Therefore, in addition to the PGM-Sb alloyed phase active sites, the interface between the PGM and Sb₂O₃ also facilitates the oxidation of pre-adsorbed CO. Interestingly, the onset of CO oxidation on Pt₅PdSb₄/C occurred at a lower potential than that of DME oxidation. This suggests that the anodic current obtained during DME oxidation is not merely due to the oxidation of CO to CO₂ but also due to the oxidation of other intermediates (–CH₃O_{ads}, –CH₂O_{ads}, and –CH₃ads) and therefore depends on their reaction over potentials [57].

3.2. Temperature dependency of DME electrooxidation

The dependence of the oxidation temperature on the activity of the Pt₅PdSb₄/C catalyst towards DME oxidation is displayed in Fig. S6a. It is observed that the activity of the current density increased from 50 to 90 mA cm⁻² with an increase in the temperature from 20 to 60 °C. Moreover, the peak current density cathodically shifted by 50 mV in the temperature range. It is reported that higher temperature facilitates water activation, which results in –OH_{ads} formation, hence the removal of surface poisoning species such as CO_{ads} [6]. The activation energy, E_a, was calculated using the Arrhenius equation (equation (7)).

$$E_a = -2.303 \times R \times m \quad (7)$$

Where R is the universal gas constant and m is the slope of the Arrhenius plot obtained by plotting log j vs. 1/T (Fig. S6b). The E_a calculated from the direct linear relationship of log j vs. 1/T at 0.75 V was 17.7 kJ mol⁻¹ which is lower than the previously reported E_a values of DME oxidation on other ternary metal catalysts, indicating the more facile DME oxidation on this catalyst [23].

3.3. Constant potential stability tests of Pt₅PdSb₄/C

The stability of Pt₅PdSb₄/C was examined by prolonged chronoamperometry measurements. Fig. 1e displays the anodic current measured at a constant potential ramp of 0.8 V in DME-saturated 0.5 M H₂SO₄ for more than 10 h. This applied potential, is in the vicinity of the DME oxidation peak potential (0.75–0.8 V) (Fig. 1a), ensuring an

accelerated durability test which was carried out during the complete oxidation of DME. Despite the rapid decline in the measured anodic current density in the first 4 h, the catalyst showed a higher steady state DME oxidation current (11.78 A g_{PGM}⁻¹) than the most active catalyst, Pt₃Pd₃Sn₂/C, reported before (9.03 A g_{PGM}⁻¹) [23]. This suggests that the Pt₅PdSb₄/C catalyst has a relatively higher sustained activity towards DME oxidation and improved resistance to surface poisoning intermediates (–CH₃O_{ads}, –CH₂O_{ads}, and –CH₃ads) which were suggested by the DFT calculations presented below (section 3.6). It is presumed that the surface Sb₂O₃ (seen in the XPS results) in the vicinity of the binary phases detected by XRD (Pt₃Sb, Pt₅Sb, PdSb₂, and Pd₃Sb) assisted in the oxidative removal of these intermediates because of its oxophilic nature.

3.4. Characterization

3.4.1. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Fig. 3a shows the XRD pattern of the polyol-synthesized Pt₅PdSb₄/C catalyst and the binary phases. The characteristic XRD peaks that appeared at 2θ = 40°, 46.4°, 67.6°, 81.5°, and 85.9° corresponded to the face-centered cubic crystal structure of PtPd: (111), (200), (220), (311), and (222) planes of the nanoparticles [58]. However, one can see that the XRD patterns of the ternary metal catalyst showed a 0.5°–1.5° negative 2θ shift relative to that of the PtPd nanoparticles. The atomic radius of Sb (2.46 Å) is larger than Pt (2.30 Å) and Pd (2.15 Å) [59]. Therefore, the incorporation of Sb into PtPd resulted in lattice expansion of the alloy and hence shifted the diffraction peaks to lower 2θ angles, suggesting the presence of ternary metal alloys [60]. A combination of tetragonal trapezohedral ternary phase Pt₃PdSb₃ (Genkinite) (PDF 00-029-0133) [61] and binary phases such as tetragonal Pt₃Sb (PDF 00-046-1066) [62], cubic PdSb₂ (Geversite) (PDF 00-003-1178), tetragonal PtSb (PDF 00-046-1065) [62], and Pd₃Sb (Stibiopalladinite) (PDF 00-014-0016) [63] were observed in the Pt₅PdSb₄ catalyst. It was difficult to assign some of the peaks to either the Pt_xSb_y or Pd_xSb_y phases since Pt and Pd have cubic structures with negligible shifts resulting from Sb alloying.

The average crystallite sizes calculated using Scherrer's equation applied to the (220) plane for PtPd/C, PtSb/C, and Pt₅PdSb₄/C are 8.5, 4.8, and 4.4 nm, respectively. The larger crystallite size of PtPd/C could be due to the more crystalline structure of the nanoparticles, as seen in the lower full-width half maximum (FWHM = 1.18) compared to PtSb/C (FWHM = 2.05) and Pt₅PdSb₄/C (FWHM = 2.23). The lattice parameter of the unit cell for Pt₅PdSb₄/C (a = b = 7.73 Å, c = 24.16 Å) is larger than PtPd/C (a = b = c = 4.08 Å). The larger lattice parameter of Pt₅PdSb₄/C compared to that of PtPd/C validates the lattice expansion due to Sb incorporation. According to Strasser et al.'s study on the reactivity-strain relationship, the expansion of the lattice strain affects the electronic band structure of platinum improving the adsorption of chemical reactants on the catalytic surface [64].

3.4.2. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS)

SAXS analysis was performed for the powder form of Pt₅PdSb₄/C and its dispersion in isopropanol at a low concentration (0.02 wt%). The processed experimental profile after background subtraction, corresponds to Pt₅PdSb₄ nanoparticles only (Fig. 3b). The calculated SAXS-based volume-weighted PSD of the metal nanoparticles in the powder (blue trace in Fig. 3b) is between 5 nm and 20 nm, which is in relatively good accordance with the PSD data derived from independent TEM study (inset graph in Fig. 3c). Fig. 3b also shows that in the high-q region, the scattering profile of the Pt₅PdSb₄ nanoparticles on a double logarithmic scale is approximately linear with a slope of –4, corresponding to the Porod's law (I ~ q⁻⁴). This feature indicates the existence of solid particles with sharp interfaces [65].

3.4.3. Electron microscopy (HR-TEM and STEM)

HR-TEM images at different magnifications and STEM images of the

Fig. 3. (a) XRD patterns of Pt₅PdSb₄/C with phases present indicated. Inset in (a); magnified XRD pattern at the 2θ region 63–71°. (b) Experimental SAXS profiles of Pt₅PdSb₄ nanoparticles with overlaid fitted model profiles in Irena software and the resulting log-normal volume-weighted size distributions of the metal nanoparticles in the powder. (c) HR-TEM image of the Pt₅PdSb₄/C at varying magnifications and SAED pattern. Inset in (c); the histogram showing the particle size distribution.

Fig. 4. (a) Survey spectrum of Pt₅PdSb₄/C and the deconvoluted XPS spectrum of (b) Pt4f, (c) Pd3d, and (d) Sb3d.

Pt₅PdSb₄/C catalyst are shown in Fig. 3c and Fig. S7, respectively. The distribution of the nanoparticles (dark black) on Vulcan XC72 (light black) shows some local agglomerations in both microscopy methods. The elemental analysis by Energy Dispersive Spectroscopic (EDS) mapping (Fig. S8) and ICP-OES (Table S3) confirmed the presence of metals (Pt, Pd, and Sb) in the expected ratios of the synthesized catalysts. Moreover, the elemental maps secured from EDS (Fig. S9) confirm that the Pt₅PdSb₄ catalyst was indeed obtained by this solvothermal method with a uniform distribution of Pt, Pd, and Sb. The particles had a narrow size distribution ranging from 5 nm to 18 nm. The average particle diameter calculated by picking 100 random particles from the images of the HR-TEM and STEM was 8.1 and 8.2 nm as shown in the inset histogram in Fig. 3c and Fig. S7, respectively. HR-TEM and STEM image analyses indicated that even though the majority of the particles were spherical (magnified section of inset Fig. S7a), a few elliptical and rod-shaped particles were formed during synthesis. The electron diffraction analysis was performed on the HR-TEM images to analyze the crystal structure of Pt₅PdSb₄/C. The indexed selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern is displayed in Fig. 3c. The interplanar spacing of the catalyst according to the dominant Genkenite facet (314) was 0.226 nm nearly similar to the reported value (0.226 nm) for Sn-based ternary catalyst (Pt₃Pd₃Sn₂/C) [23].

3.4.4. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

The wide-spectrum XPS spectra of the Pt₅PdSb₄/C catalyst displayed in Fig. 4a confirm the presence of all metals at their respective binding energies. The binding energy of C1s at 284.6 eV was used as an internal standard for all the spectra. The Pt4f spectrum exhibits two major peaks at 71.3 and 74.8 eV corresponding to Pt4f_{7/2} and Pt4f_{5/2} (Fig. 4b). These peaks were assigned to metallic platinum (Pt⁰), (82 %). The spectrum at

72.1 and 76.1 eV are related to the remaining platinum (18 %) present as Pt²⁺. Only two XPS spectral signatures were observed for the Pd3d corresponding to Pd3d_{5/2} and Pd3d_{3/2} at 335.9 and 341.3 eV, respectively, and both are assigned to the metallic palladium (Pd⁰) (Fig. 4c). The existence of the majority of noble metals (Pt and Pd) in their metallic state indicates their high resistance to oxidation at potentials below 0.75 V (Fig. S2). Nevertheless, some of the Pt atoms on the surface formed partial metal-O bonds resulting in a slight shift of the spectrum to a higher binding energy, by 0.3–0.5 eV. The XPS spectra revealed two major peaks at 530.9 eV (Sb3d_{3/2}) and 540.2 eV (Sb3d_{5/2}), assigned to Sb³⁺ that makes up nearly 90 % of the antimony on the catalyst surface (Fig. 4d). The 529.3 eV and 538.8 eV deconvoluted peaks in the Sb3d spectrum correspond to metallic antimony (Sb⁰), calculated as 10 % of the antimony in the total antimony present [66].

The integrated areas of the deconvoluted XPS peaks, corresponding to the various oxidation states of the surface elements, are summarized in Table S4. According to the data in this table, the atomic ratio of Pt: Pd: Sb was 12:1:17. Notably, this outcome diverges from the bulk atomic ratio measured by ICP analysis, which is 5:1:4, showing the instability of Pd on the surface or rather the stronger interaction of PtSb.

3.5. Fuel cell testing

The polarization curves of the fuel cell operated with 100 % humidified DME (or H₂) and air supplied through the anode (Pt₅PdSb₄/C) and cathode (Pt/C) flowing at 40 and 350 mL min⁻¹, respectively, are displayed in Fig. 5a. The cell was initially operated with H₂-air to evaluate its quality and to use the results as a reference for the DDMEFC. The E_{oc} for the DME-fed fuel cell (0.932 V) is 0.32 V higher than the H₂-fed fuel cell (0.900 V) (Fig. S10). It is reported that DME crosses through

Fig. 5. (a) Polarization curves for DME-air fuel cells (anode-cathode) (DME flow at 40 mL min⁻¹ and air at 350 mL min⁻¹, respectively, cell temperature at 65 °C, anode and cathode loading of 1.2 and 3.1 mg_{PGM}⁻¹ cm⁻², respectively, and 4 cm² electrode area). (b) Current measured during potential step oxidation of DME in a half cell (DME-saturated 0.5 M H₂SO₄ circulating through the anode at 10 mL min⁻¹ and H₂ gas flowing through the cathode at 40 mL min⁻¹). (c) FTIR spectra of electrolyte samples collected after polarization at selected potential steps as shown in (b). (d) The change in the transmittance of methanol and CO₂, along with current as a function of the applied potentials.

the Nafion membrane leading to mixed potential that occurs at the cathode [67]. However, owing to its larger size, DME crossover through the Nafion membrane is expected to be lower than hydrogen, hence the higher E_{OC} of the DME fuel cell as demonstrated by Kashyap et al. [6] who measured a higher crossover current density with H_2 (20 mA cm^{-2}) than with DME (1.5 mA cm^{-2}) under similar conditions.

DME-air and H_2 -air fuel cells produced power outputs of 180 and 250 mW cm^{-2} at 0.45 and 0.5 V, respectively, on the same electrode (Fig. S10). The lower power density measured in the H_2 -air fuel cell using our new ternary anode catalyst, Pt_5PdSb_4/C , may be attributable to several factors, including the underperformance for a hydrogen oxidation reaction of our catalyst as compared to the state-of-the-art catalyst Pt/C, composed of free Pt nanoparticles. Furthermore, the absence of H_2 backpressure during the operation of the H_2 -air fuel cell may have resulted in a sub-optimal concentration of H_2 at the catalytic interface. Additionally, the preparation of the MEA was optimized for DME-air fuel cell and not H_2 -air fuel cell. It is essential to note that the purpose of highlighting H_2 -air fuel cell performance is solely to serve as a basis for evaluating the performance of direct DME fuel cell in contrast to a contemporary H_2 -fed PEMFC. The substantial power output demonstrated by the direct gas-fed DME fuel cell - which is 71 % of the power output of a pure hydrogen fuel cell tested on the same cell, undoubtedly provides strong evidence for the significant potential of this biofuel as a substitute for H_2 . The current density obtained at 0.5 V for the previously reported DDMEFC using different catalysts was compared with that of our catalyst (Table 2). It can be observed that, at the selected potential value, Pt_5PdSb_4/C provided the highest (360 mA cm^{-2}) reported current density.

We conducted an examination of the impact of temperature on the performance of DDMEFC over a range of 25–80 °C (Fig. S11). At a temperature of 25 °C, the DDMEFC exhibited a relatively low power density of $68 \text{ mW mg}_{PGM}^{-1}$ at 0.41 V. As the temperature increased, the power density demonstrated a corresponding increase, reaching a maximum of $192 \text{ mW mg}_{PGM}^{-1}$ at 0.45 V.

3.6. Fuel cell stability and recovery

As observed in aqueous solutions, the catalyst also demonstrated a decrease in activity within the DDMEFC configuration, likely due to the presence of surface-poisoning intermediates. The current density experienced a continuous decline and ultimately reached nearly zero after 1 h of operating the DDMEFC at a constant potential of 0.8 V (see Fig. S12a). A negligible power output was also recorded after this 1-h period, as indicated in the inset of Fig. S12b. Despite this degradation, the catalyst's activity, and subsequently, the power output of the DDMEFC, was restored by flushing the anode with H_2 gas for 15 min following the chronoamperometry measurement. The H_2 flow was then terminated, and the DME flow was resumed for 30 min to ensure complete evacuation of any residual H_2 prior to initiating the polarization data recording. As depicted in Fig. S12b, 95 % of the peak power density was regained after the anode was flushed with H_2 gas. To further

elucidate the chemical reaction of reaction intermediate with H_2 gas, the fuel cell anode exhaust gases during H_2 flow were monitored by connecting the outlet to a mass spectrometer. As shown in Fig. S13, the initiation of H_2 gas flow resulted in the detection of formaldehyde, confirmed by the increase in its signal. The formation mechanism of formaldehyde involves the reduction of the intermediate such as CO formed upon oxidation of DME according to eq (8). This observation is substantiated by the literature reports that have found low-temperature (<100 °C) hydrogenation of CO in the aqueous phase to formaldehyde in the presence of catalytic metals such as Pd and Ru [70,71].

The reaction thermodynamics indicates that ΔG of CO to HCHO in the aqueous phase is negative at low temperatures and the equilibrium constant being relatively high (17.33 mol^{-1} at 298 K) should favor the formation of HCHO. Further, since the heat of the solution of HCHO (-62 kJ mol^{-1}) is relatively high in comparison with the heat of the solution of H_2 and CO, the formation of HCHO is favored.

Since 0.8 V is too high for reliable chronoamperometry and potential application in fuel cell technology, we conducted chronoamperometry at a lower potential (0.4 V) instead of the initial chronoamperometry recorded at 0.8 V. It was observed that, unlike the DDMEFC operated at 0.8 V, where the current density steadily declined to nearly zero within 1 h, the DDMEFC operated at 0.4 V exhibited greater stability, maintaining a current density of 135 mA cm^{-2} after 1 h of operation (Fig. S12a).

3.7. DME oxidation mechanism: ex-situ FTIR

A limited number of studies have reported the oxidation mechanism of DME on different catalysts by examining the electrode surface in an aqueous liquid electrolyte or the anode exhaust from a DME-operated fuel cell using FTIR. In an ideal case, direct oxidation of dimethyl ether to CO_2 will result in improved fuel cell power output and stable voltage. However, the catalytic electrodes reported in this work and earlier works including the state-of-the-art catalysts activate DME only through indirect pathways leading to some loss of fuel conversion efficiency [72–74]. Müller et al. [72] reported that DME adsorbed on the catalyst surface reacted with one water molecule to produce Pt-CHO and CH_3OH . Pt-CHO dehydrogenates to Pt-CO, which further oxidizes to CO_2 by the activation of a water molecule and CH_3OH either reacts in the anode via the six-electron pathway, crossover to the cathode side of the fuel cell through the Nafion membrane or leaves the anode side unreacted. The DME oxidation mechanism proposed by Kerangueven [73] describes the C-adsorption of DME on Pt which hydrolyzes to form the surface-adsorbed intermediate CH_2OH_{ads} . Continued dehydrogenation of CH_2OH_{ads} can result in the formation of CO_{ads} or CHO_{ads} , which are then oxidized to CO_2 or $HCOOH$ upon reaction with non-activated water molecules at low potentials (<0.3 V). At more positive potentials (>0.55 V), CO_{ads} or CHO_{ads} were removed from the surface by the activated water (OH_{ads}) in the form of CO_2 .

Table 2

Comparison of electrochemical performance outputs obtained at 0.5 V using selected anode catalysts for DDMEFCs.

Parameters	PtRu black	$Pt_{46}Ru_{44}Pd_{10}/C$	$SnO_2/Pt/C$	$Pt_{0.75}Pd_{0.25}/SnO_2/C$	$Pt_3Pd_3Sn_2/C$	Pt_5PdSb_4/C
Anode loading ($mg_{PGM} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	4	4.24	1.23	1.20	1.6	1.2
Cathode loading ($mg_{Pt} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	4	2	3.50	3.50	3.7	3.1
Air/ O_2 flow rate (mL min^{-1})	300	500	300	400	350	350
DME flowrate (mL min^{-1})	1.20	40	15	40	40	40
Cell temperature (°C)	80	80	70	70	80	65
Backpressure (bar)	2	1.40	0	0	0	0
^a Peak power density (mW mg_{PGM}^{-1})	19	28	85	90	135	150
^{**} Peak power density (mW mg_{PGM}^{-1})	9.40	19	22.20	23	40.75	42
Current density @ 0.5 V (mA cm^{-2})	100	150	190	200	385	360
References	[68]	[69]	[57]	[6]	[23]	This study

^a Normalized to the anode PGM loading; ^{**}Normalized to anode + cathode PGM loadings.

Fig. 5c shows the ex-situ FTIR spectra of the anode outlet collected from a DME-fed fuel cell, as described in the experimental section and shown in Fig. S1. The spectra appearing at 1085 and 1163 cm^{-1} were attributed to the $\nu(\text{C-O-C})$ and $\nu(\text{CH}_3)$ vibration modes of DME [75]. The peak at 1480 cm^{-1} which appears at 0.6 and 0.8 V but disappears at more positive potentials is assigned to the $\delta(\text{CH}_3)$ vibration modes of DME [75]. An observed spectrum corresponding to the C=O vibration of methyl formate, starting at 0.6 V, is identified at approximately 1730 cm^{-1} [76]. The bands near the 2850 and 2900 cm^{-1} clearly visible at 0.2 and 0.4 V, respectively, are associated with the CH vibration of CH_3OH and CHOOH [77]. Hence, it can be concluded that methanol and formic acid are formed in this potential region. The formation of methyl formate is through the esterification of the methanol and formic acid, as we reported previously [74]. The nearly 6.0 and 7.8 mA currents observed at 0.2 and 0.4 V, respectively (Fig. 5b and d), are due to the formation of methanol and formic acid. The intensity of these peaks experienced a notable reduction at 0.6 V and vanished at higher potentials. This trend is apparent in the declining transmittance signal shown in Fig. 5d. This phenomenon was accompanied by a rapid drop in the transmittance of the peak observed at 2350 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the O=C=O of dissolved CO_2 , indicating the conversion of methanol and formic acid into CO_2 [78]. Nevertheless, the production of CO_2 slowed down beyond 0.8 V, as seen by the rise in its transmittance that followed the current decrease (Fig. 5d). The decline in the current density beyond 0.8 V is due to the coverage of the catalyst with surface oxides making it less active for DME oxidation [23].

3.8. DFT calculations

DFT calculations were conducted to investigate the optimal configuration, adsorption, and oxidation of DME on Pt_5PdSb_4 . Several adsorption sites, P1-P4, were considered for the DME molecule. The structures and adsorption energies are listed in Table 3. Oxygen (O) was adsorbed atop antimony (Sb) at sites P1-P3. At P1, both methyl groups reside over platinum (Pt). Meanwhile, on P2, one methyl group is situated over Pt, whereas the other was positioned above palladium (Pd). At location P3, one methyl group is found over Pt, whereas the other was located above the hollow site. At P4, O is adsorbed on top of the Sb atom protruding from the surface. The best adsorption site (with the most negative adsorption energy) is P2 (Table 3). This adsorption orientation was also seen in the ternary alloy of Pt_2PdPb_2 alloy [74]. The adsorption energy of DME was -0.60 eV, which is higher than that of DME adsorption on previously reported ternary alloys, $\text{Pt}_3\text{Pd}_3\text{Sn}_2$ (-0.83 eV) [23] and PtPdPb (0.90) [74]. As the adsorption energy of DME on Pt_5PdSb_4 alloy is higher, it is easier to oxidize DME, as evidenced by the higher stable current density obtained with Pt_5PdSb_4 (11.78 $\text{A g}_{\text{PGM}}^{-1}$) than with $\text{Pt}_3\text{Pd}_3\text{Sn}_2$ (9.03 $\text{A g}_{\text{PGM}}^{-1}$) [23] and Pt_2PdPb_2 (7.46 $\text{A g}_{\text{PGM}}^{-1}$) [74] at 0.8 V. A higher adsorption energy implies weaker adsorption leading to enhanced oxidation of DME.

Scheme S1a and b summarize the reaction energies for all relevant steps in the DME oxidation to CO_2 at 0.0 V. The Pt_5PdSb_4 surface facilitated two competitive elementary reactions as the initial steps of DME oxidation, as depicted in Scheme S1a. The first can be an electrochemical step in which a hydrogen atom from the methyl group at the top site of Pt is dissociated, which requires 0.27 eV. Alternatively, the C-

Table 3

Adsorption site of DME on the XRD-dominated plane of Pt_5PdSb_4 (314) (Blue – Pt, orange – Sb, grey – Pd, red – O, brown – C, white – H).

Site name	Top view	Side view	Adsorption energy (eV)
P1			-0.53
P2			-0.56
P3			-0.36
P4			n.c. ^a

^a n.c. - failed to converge.

O bond can be cleaved, resulting in a methyl (CH_3) group on a Pt atom and a methoxy group (CH_3O) on the Sb atom, this is a non-electrochemical step requiring 0.32 eV, only 0.05 eV more than the electrochemical step. Both alternative steps are endergonic and are very close in energy. However, when a potential is applied, the electrochemical step (dissociation of hydrogen) becomes more favorable.

In the subsequent step, which requires 0.64 eV, a hydrogen atom is removed from a different methyl group, leading to CH_2OCH_2 formation adsorbed onto Pt and Pd through carbon atoms. Further oxidation proceeds in either C-O bond cleavage resulting in the formation of CH_2O and CH_2 (requires 0.55 eV) or in an electrochemical C-H cleavage forming CH_2OCH at the Pt side (requires 0.64 eV). Although C-H cleavage is slightly higher in energy by 0.09 eV, this reaction is predominant at higher potentials (>0.6 V). CH_2OCH is further oxidized only by C-O cleavage, resulting in the formation of CH_2O and CH , with a release of -0.19 eV.

The oxidation of CH_3 , CH_2 , CH_3O , CH_2O , and CH residues and their further oxidation were studied as well. These species remain adsorbed on the electrode surface in the CCM. Since the ex-situ FTIR analysis was conducted in an aqueous solution collected from the fuel cell exit, these species could not be detected by the FTIR. Nevertheless, CH_3 reacts readily with an adsorbed hydroxide to form methanol in an exergonic reaction of -0.13 eV, a reaction that led to the formation of the methanol detected in the aqueous solution by ex-situ FTIR. The formation of CH_2 was impossible as the release of hydrogen was highly endergonic (2.41 eV). Fig. 6 illustrates the energy diagram of the CH and CH_2O oxidation process at 0.0 V and 0.6 V. CH adsorbed onto Pt is easily oxidized to CHOH in an exergonic (-0.55 eV) reaction. The release of hydrogen to form a single carbon is an endergonic reaction that requires 0.21 eV, which probably does not occur. Subsequently, CHOH loses the hydroxylic hydrogen atom to form CHO with a reaction energy of -1.41 eV. Similarly, CH_2O also loses a hydrogen atom to form CHO with a reaction energy of 0.59 eV.

Dehydrogenation and formation of CO is an endergonic reaction (0.35 eV) while a reaction with $^*\text{OH}$ and formation of formic acid (CHOOH) is an exergonic reaction with an energy of -0.15 eV, this is the predominant reaction at low potentials. When a potential of 0.6 V is applied, the CO formation energy decreases to -0.25 eV, as this reaction is potentially dependent, while the formation of formic acid is not potential dependent. Thus, at a potential of 0.6 V, the formation of CO is preferred; however, the adsorbed CO is readily oxidized to form COOH , with an energy of -0.64 eV.

Formic acid detected in the anode exhaust was the result of this

reaction. Once formic acid is formed, C-H cleavage (-0.15 eV) is more plausible than O-H cleavage (1.09 eV), and COOH is formed from either CO or formic acid. In the following step, the last hydrogen is released, and the CO_2 formed is released from the surface in an endergonic reaction of -0.59 , evidenced by its presence in the anode outlet.

The configurations of all relevant species are listed in Table S5. The electrooxidation of DME and the residues at 0.00 V are shown in Fig. 6. The oxidation of the residues requires the adsorption of OH on the particles' surface. These OH^* species were formed by water activation on PtPdSb, which requires 0.36 eV. Without applying potential, the splitting of water is not possible. H_2O was adsorbed on the surface, with an adsorption energy of -0.02 eV. The splitting of water is potential-dependent and at 0.6 V it is exothermic by -0.24 eV. Water splitting was required to obtain formic acid from CHO , as shown in Fig. 6. At this stage, the energy of the system is lowered to -1.58 eV (Fig. 6) due to exothermic reactions that occur prior to the formation of CHO . This energy enables the splitting of water and enhances DME oxidation.

4. Conclusion

We examined the electrooxidation of DME on Vulcan XC72-supported Sb-based novel ternary metal catalysts ($\text{Pt}_x\text{Pd}_y\text{Sb}_z/\text{C}$) synthesized by thermal (180 °C) and ethylene glycol reduction method both in a three-electrode cell and a 4 cm^2 single fuel cell. The expected atomic ratios of these metals in the catalyst were confirmed using elemental analysis (ICP-OES and EDS). Extensive physico-chemical characterizations of the selected catalyst, $\text{Pt}_5\text{PdSb}_4/\text{C}$, (which showed the best performance in terms of DME oxidation current and oxidation charge in aqueous solution) were conducted using XRD, SAXS, STEM, and XPS. XRD revealed that binary ($\text{Pt}_3\text{Sb}/\text{Pd}_3\text{Sb}$, PtSb , and PdSb_2) and ternary (Pt_3PdSb_3) phases were present in the synthesized catalyst. The average particle size of the catalyst, as measured by SAXS and electron microscopy (STEM and HR-TEM), of the catalyst was approximately 8 nm, which is slightly larger than that of previously reported ternary metal catalysts. XPS measurements suggest that a significant amount of the surface was in the form of Sb_2O_3 , in contact with the binary phases that improved the CO tolerance of the catalyst, as evidenced by the pre-adsorbed CO stripping experiment. $\text{Pt}_5\text{PdSb}_4/\text{C}$ showed a nearly 0.3 V negative shift in the CO oxidation onset potential compared to that of commercial Pt/C. The catalyst exhibited long-term (>10 h) durability in a conventional three-electrode cell with a stable current density of 11.78 $\text{A g}_{\text{Pt}}^{-1}$. Moreover, in a DDMEFC, $\text{Pt}_5\text{PdSb}_4/\text{C}$ provided the highest reported current density (430 mA cm^{-2} at 0.5 V) in comparison with other

Fig. 6. The free energy landscapes (in eV) of the oxidation process on Pt_5PtSb_4 at 0.0 V and 0.6 V. Numerals indicate the ΔG^0 values of the reaction in eV units.

previously reported ternary catalysts at the same potential. *Ex-situ* FTIR analysis and theoretical DFT calculations showed that methanol and formic acid were formed by the subsequent oxidation of CH₃ and CHO intermediates, respectively, and that hydroxide ions were produced by water activation. Functional groups corresponding to CO₂ were detected in the higher potential regions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Medhanie Gebremedhin Gebru: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Itay Pitussi:** Investigation. **Hanan Teller:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Formal analysis. **Achyuth Marammuriyan Chathoth:** Data curation, Formal analysis. **Haya Kornweitz:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Formal analysis. **Rostislav Medlín:** Investigation. **Petr Bělský:** Investigation. **Palaniappan Subramanian:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Alex Schechter:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to acknowledge Ariel University, Israel National Research Center for Electrochemical Propulsion (INREP), and the New Technologies Research Centre, University of West Bohemia, Pilsen for financially supporting this research. The authors would also like to acknowledge the Ariel HPC Center at Ariel University for providing computing resources. Part of the result was developed within the project Quantum materials for applications in sustainable technologies (QM4ST), reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004572 by P JAK, call Excellent Research. P.S. thanks the financial support provided by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic - Delta 2 program for the project "Advanced Graphene Electrode Architecture for Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell, ref no, TM05000013.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.236301>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] S. Sharma, S.K. Ghoshal, Hydrogen the future transportation fuel: from production to applications, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 43 (2015) 1151–1158, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.11.093>.
- [2] S. Singh, S. Jain, V. Ps, A.K. Tiwari, M.R. Nouni, J.K. Pandey, S. Goel, Hydrogen: a sustainable fuel for future of the transport sector, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 51 (2015) 623–633, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.06.040>.
- [3] M.S. Alias, S.K. Kamarudin, A.M. Zainoodin, M.S. Masdar, Active direct methanol fuel cell: an overview, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 45 (2020) 19620–19641, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.04.202>.
- [4] S.P.S. Badwal, S. Giddey, A. Kulkarni, J. Goel, S. Basu, Direct ethanol fuel cells for transport and stationary applications - a comprehensive review, *Appl. Energy* 145 (2015) 80–103, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.02.002>.
- [5] J. Zhang, M. Chen, H. Li, Y. Li, J. Ye, Z. Cao, M. Fang, Q. Kuang, J. Zheng, Z. Xie, Stable palladium hydride as a superior anode electrocatalyst for direct formic acid fuel cells, *Nano Energy* 44 (2018) 127–134, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2017.11.075>.
- [6] D. Kashyap, H. Teller, A. Schechter, Highly active Pt_xPd_y/SnO₂/C catalyst for dimethyl ether oxidation in fuel cells, *J. Power Sources* 396 (2018) 335–344, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2018.06.002>.
- [7] K.T. Møller, T.R. Jensen, E. Akiba, H. wen Li, Hydrogen - a sustainable energy carrier, *Prog. Nat. Sci. Mater. Int.* 27 (2017) 34–40, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PNSC.2016.12.014>.
- [8] X. Zhen, Y. Wang, An overview of methanol as an internal combustion engine fuel, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 52 (2015) 477–493, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2015.07.083>.
- [9] J.E. Logsdon, Ethanol, kirk-othmer encycl, *Chem. Technol.* (2000), <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471238961.0520080112150719.a01>.
- [10] O. Siddiqui, I. Dincer, Investigation of a new anion exchange membrane-based direct ammonia fuel cell system, *Fuel Cell.* 18 (2018) 379–388, <https://doi.org/10.1002/FUCE.201800052>.
- [11] G.H. El-Nowihy, M.S. El-Deab, Smart selection of fuel blends: robust oxidation of formic acid in its blend with urea at NiOx/Pd nanoparticles-based binary anodes, *Renew. Energy* 167 (2021) 830–840, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RENENE.2020.11.156>.
- [12] S.H. Park, C.S. Lee, Applicability of dimethyl ether (DME) in a compression ignition engine as an alternative fuel, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 86 (2014) 848–863, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2014.06.051>.
- [13] Q. Li, X. Wen, G. Wu, H.T. Chung, R. Gao, P. Zelenay, High-activity PtRuPd/C catalyst for direct dimethyl ether fuel cells, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 54 (2015) 7524–7528, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201500454>.
- [14] Q. Li, G. Wu, C.M. Johnston, P. Zelenay, Direct dimethyl ether fuel cell with much improved performance, *Electrocatalysis* 5 (2014) 310–317, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12678-014-0196-z>.
- [15] G. Bin Jung, A. Su, C.H. Tu, F.B. Weng, S.H. Chen, R.Y. Lee, S.H. Wu, Supported Nafion membrane for direct methanol fuel cell, *J. Fuel Cell Sci. Technol.* 4 (2007) 248–254, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2743069>.
- [16] K. Tonnis, Z. Nan, J. Fang, R. Pavlicek, E.S. Decastro, A.P. Angelopoulos, Aqueous synthesis of highly dispersed Pt₂Bi alloy nanoplatelets for dimethyl ether electro-oxidation, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* 3 (2020) 7588–7600, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.0c01028>.
- [17] L.T. Roling, J.A. Herron, W. Budiman, P. Ferrin, M. Mavrikakis, Dimethyl ether electro-oxidation on platinum surfaces, *Nano Energy* 29 (2016) 428–438, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2016.02.041>.
- [18] J.A. Herron, P. Ferrin, M. Mavrikakis, First-principles mechanistic analysis of dimethyl ether electro-oxidation on monometallic single-crystal surfaces, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 118 (2014) 24199–24211, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp505919x>.
- [19] B. Gavriel, R. Sharabi, L. Elbaz, Direct electro-oxidation of dimethyl ether on Pt–Cu nanochains, *ChemSusChem* 10 (2017) 3069–3074, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201700702>.
- [20] H. Teller, D. Kashyap, S.O. Danino, A. Schechter, Ultra-low loading of highly active Pt and PtSn catalysts on hierarchical tin as anodes in direct methanol fuel cells, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 165 (2018) F1242–F1248, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.1181814JES/XML>.
- [21] M. Kübler, T. Jurzinsky, D. Ziegenbalg, C. Cremers, Methanol oxidation reaction on core-shell structured Ruthenium-Palladium nanoparticles: relationship between structure and electrochemical behavior, *J. Power Sources* 375 (2018) 320–334, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.07.114>.
- [22] G. Kerangueven, C. Coutanceau, E. Sibert, J.M. Léger, C. Lamy, Methoxy methane (dimethyl ether) as an alternative fuel for direct fuel cells, *J. Power Sources* 157 (2006) 318–324, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2005.07.080>.
- [23] D. Kashyap, H. Teller, P. Subramanian, B. Petr, M.G. Gebru, I. Pitussi, R.S. Yadav, H. Kornweitz, A. Schechter, Sn-based atokite alloy nanocatalyst for high-power dimethyl ether fueled low-temperature polymer electrolyte fuel cell, *J. Power Sources* 544 (2022) 231882, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.231882>.
- [24] V.B. Kumar, D. Kashyap, H. Teller, M.G. Gebru, A. Gedanken, A. Schechter, Methyl formate and dimethyl ether electro-oxidation on Pt–Pd–Sn catalyst supported on carbon nanotube decorated with carbon dots, *Mater. Today Sustain.* 17 (2022) 100095, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtsust.2021.100095>.
- [25] E.H. Kong, F. Maimani, G.K.S. Prakash, P.D. Ronney, Dynamics of direct hydrocarbon PEM fuel cells, *Sci. Rep.* (2024) 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-68832-7>.
- [26] J.O. Jensen, A. Vassiliev, M.I. Olsen, Q.F. Li, C. Pan, L.N. Cleemann, T. Steenberg, H.A. Hjuler, N.J. Bjerrum, Direct dimethyl ether fueling of a high temperature polymer fuel cell, *J. Power Sources* 211 (2012) 173–176, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2012.03.039>.
- [27] L. Zhang, D. Xia, Electrocatalytic activity of ordered intermetallic PtSb for methanol electro-oxidation, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 252 (2006) 2191–2195, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2005.03.221>.
- [28] X. Yu, P.G. Pickup, Pb and Sb modified Pt/C catalysts for direct formic acid fuel cells, *Electrochim. Acta* 55 (2010) 7354–7361, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2010.07.019>.
- [29] X. Yu, P.G. Pickup, Deactivation resistant PdSb/C catalysts for direct formic acid fuel cells, *Electrochem. Commun.* 12 (2010) 800–803, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elecom.2010.03.037>.
- [30] J. Cai, Y. Huang, Y. Guo, Facile synthesis of PdSb/C nanocatalyst with high performance for ethanol electro-oxidation in alkaline medium, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 39 (2014) 18256–18263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.09.011>.
- [31] M. Gebremedhin Gebru, R. Shyam Yadav, H. Teller, H. Kornweitz, P. Subramanian, A. Schechter, Harnessing dimethyl ether and methyl formate fuels for direct

- electrochemical energy conversion, *J. Energy Chem.* 83 (2023) 454–464, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEACHEM.2023.05.001>.
- [32] J. Ilavsky, P.R. Jemian, Irena: tool suite for modeling and analysis of small-angle scattering, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 42 (2009) 347–353, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0021889809002222>.
- [33] M.G. Gebru, H. Teller, P. Subramanian, A. Schechter, Nonthermal plasma-modified carbon-carrying Sn-based ternary nanocatalyst for high-performance direct dimethyl ether fuel cells, *Energy Technol.* 10 (2022) 2200835, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ente.202200835>.
- [34] J. Zhang, H. Zhang, J. Wu, J. Zhang, Techniques for PEM fuel cell testing and diagnosis, <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-444-53688-4.00003-6>, 2013.
- [35] S.Q. Song, W.J. Zhou, Z.H. Zhou, L.H. Jiang, G.Q. Sun, Q. Xin, V. Leontidis, S. Kontou, P. Tsiakaras, Direct ethanol PEM fuel cells: the case of platinum based anodes, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 30 (2005) 995–1001, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2004.11.006>.
- [36] A. Küver, I. Vogel, W. Vielstich, Distinct performance evaluation of a direct methanol SPE fuel cell. A new method using a dynamic hydrogen reference electrode, *J. Power Sources* 52 (1994) 77–80, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-7753\(94\)01943-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-7753(94)01943-6).
- [37] J.A. Sholl, D.S., *Steckel, Density Functional Theory: a Practical Introduction*, John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [38] A. Allouche, Ab-initio simulations of materials using VASP: density-functional theory and beyond, *J. Comput. Chem.* 32 (2008) 174–182, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc>.
- [39] P.E. Blöchl, Projector augmented-wave method, *Phys. Rev. B* 50 (1994) 17953–17979, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.50.17953>.
- [40] L.J. Kohn, W. Sham, Self-consistent equations including exchange and correlation effects, *Phys. Rev.* 140 (1965) A1133, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.140.A1133>.
- [41] J.P. Perdew, K. Burke, M. Ernzerhof, Generalized gradient approximation made simple, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 77 (1996) 3865, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.77.3865>.
- [42] J.D. Monkhorst, H.J. Pack, Special points for Brillouin-zone integrations, *Phys. Rev. B* 13 (1976) 5188, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8ta11250a>.
- [43] S. Grimme, J. Antony, S. Ehrlich, H. Krieg, A consistent and accurate ab initio parametrization of density functional dispersion correction (DFT-D) for the 94 elements H-Pu, *J. Chem. Phys.* 132 (2010), <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3382344>.
- [44] J.G. Bucko, T. Hafner, J. Lebegue, S. Angyan, Improved description of the structure of molecular and layered crystals: ab initio DFT calculations with van der Waals corrections, *J. Phys. Chem. A* 114 (2010) 11814–11824, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp106469x>.
- [45] K. Mathew, V.S.C. Kolluru, S. Mula, S.N. Steinmann, R.G. Hennig, Implicit self-consistent electrolyte model in plane-wave density-functional theory, *J. Chem. Phys.* 151 (2019) 234101, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5132354>.
- [46] X. Chen, J.G. Guo, C.S. Gong, J. Deng, T.P. Ying, E.J. Cheng, S.Y. Li, X.L. Chen, Pd3Te2: an s-wave superconductor with pd atom coordinated by five te atoms, *J. Phys. Commun.* 3 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1088/2399-6528/ab3fd7>.
- [47] S. Curtarolo, W. Setyawan, G.L.W. Hart, M. Jahnatek, R.V. Chepulskii, R.H. Taylor, S. Wang, J. Xue, K. Yang, O. Levy, M.J. Mehl, H.T. Stokes, D.O. Demchenko, D. Morgan, AFLOW: an automatic framework for high-throughput materials discovery, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 58 (2012) 218–226, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2012.02.005>.
- [48] Y. Wang, M. Moses-DeBusk, L. Stevens, J. Hu, P. Zavalij, K. Bowen, B.I. Dunlap, E. R. Glaser, B. Eichhorn, Sb@Ni12@Sb20-/+ and Sb@Pd12@Sb20n cluster anions, where n = +1, -1, -3, -4: multi-oxidation-state clusters of interpenetrating platonic solids, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 139 (2017) 619–622, <https://doi.org/10.1021/JACS.6B12109>.
- [49] B. Gavriel, R. Sharabi, L. Elbaz, Direct electro-oxidation of dimethyl ether on Pt–Cu nanochains, *ChemSusChem* 10 (2017) 3069–3074, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201700702>.
- [50] N. Chandrasekhar, D.S. Sholl, Quantitative computational screening of Pd-based intermetallic membranes for hydrogen separation, *J. Memb. Sci.* 453 (2014) 516–524, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2013.11.032>.
- [51] M.H. Shao, K. Sasaki, R.R. Adzic, Pd-Fe nanoparticles as electrocatalysts for oxygen reduction, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 128 (2006) 3526–3527, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja060167d>.
- [52] J.H. Dumont, U. Martinez, H.T. Chung, P. Zelenay, Ternary PtRuPd/C catalyst for high-performance, low-temperature direct dimethyl ether fuel cells, *Chemelectrochem* 3 (2016) 1564–1569, <https://doi.org/10.1002/celec.201600336>.
- [53] Y. Zhang, L. Lu, Y. Tong, M. Osawa, S. Ye, Electrochemical and infrared study of electro-oxidation of dimethyl ether (DME) on platinum polycrystalline electrode in acid solutions, *Electrochim. Acta* 53 (2008) 6093–6103, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ELECTACTA.2008.01.109>.
- [54] B. Shabani, M. Hafitanian, S. Khamani, A. Ramiar, A.A. Ranjbar, Poisoning of proton exchange membrane fuel cells by contaminants and impurities: review of mechanisms, effects, and mitigation strategies, *J. Power Sources* 427 (2019) 21–48, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.03.097>.
- [55] D.W. Lee, D. Choi, M.J. Lee, H. Jin, S. Lee, I. Jang, H.Y. Park, J.H. Jang, H.J. Kim, K.Y. Lee, S.J. Yoo, Tailoring of Pt island RuO₂/C catalysts by galvanic replacement to achieve superior hydrogen oxidation reaction and CO poisoning resistance, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* 4 (2021) 8098–8107, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.1c01397>.
- [56] R.S. Yadav, M.G. Gebru, H. Teller, A. Schechter, H. Kornweitz, Correction: the origins of formic acid electrooxidation on selected surfaces of Pt, Pd, and their alloys with Sn, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 12 (2024) 3750, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4TA90022G>.
- [57] D. Kashyap, H. Teller, A. Schechter, Dimethyl ether oxidation on an active SnO₂/Pt/C catalyst for high-power fuel cells, *Chemelectrochem* 6 (2019) 2407–2414, <https://doi.org/10.1002/celec.201900216>.
- [58] L.K. Hanawalt, J.D. Rinn, H.W. Frevel, Chemical analysis by X-ray diffraction: classification and use of X-ray diffraction patterns, *Powder Diffr.* 1 (1986) 2–14, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0885715600011490>.
- [59] M. Rahm, R. Hoffmann, N.W. Ashcroft, Atomic and ionic radii of elements 1–96, *Chem. Eur. J.* 22 (2016) 14625–14632, <https://doi.org/10.1002/CHEM.201602949>.
- [60] X. Wang, F. Zhu, Y. He, M. Wang, Z. Zhang, Z. Ma, R. Li, Highly active carbon supported ternary PdSnPt_x (x = 0.1–0.7) catalysts for ethanol electro-oxidation in alkaline and acid media, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 468 (2016) 200–210, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2016.01.068>.
- [61] J.T. Cabri, L.J. Stewart, J.M. Laflamme, J.H.G. Szymanski, Platinum-group minerals from Onverwacht; III, Genkinit, (Pt (Pt, Pd) 4 Sb 3, a new mineral, *Can. Mineral.* 15 (1977) 389–392, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/258210477>. (Accessed 22 August 2023).
- [62] G.Y. Kim, W.S. Chao, G.Y. Chao, Phase relations in the system Pt-Sb-Te, *Can. Mineral.* 28 (1990) 675–685.
- [63] R.M. Berry, L.G. Thompson, X-ray powder data for the ore minerals. *The Peacock Atlas*, Geological Society of America, 1962.
- [64] P. Strasser, S. Koh, T. Anniyev, J. Greeley, K. More, C. Yu, Z. Liu, S. Kaya, D. Nordlund, H. Ogasawara, M.F. Toney, A. Nilsson, Lattice-strain control of the activity in dealloyed core-shell fuel cell catalysts, *Nat. Chem.* 2 (2010) 454–460, <https://doi.org/10.1038/NCHEM.623>.
- [65] T. Li, A.J. Senesi, B. Lee, Small angle X-ray scattering for nanoparticle Research, *Chem. Rev.* 116 (2016) 11128–11180, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.5b00690>.
- [66] A.S. Haidyrah, N. Karikalan, R. Karthik, J.J. Shim, C.C. Yang, C. Karupiah, Surface sulfuration of antimony oxide enhances the electrochemical determination of acetabulol in biomedical samples, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 894 (2021) 115371, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JELECHEM.2021.115371>.
- [67] C. Simari, I. Nicotera, A.S. Aricò, V. Baglio, F. Lufrano, New insights into properties of methanol transport in sulfonated polysulfone composite membranes for direct methanol fuel cells, *Polymers* 13 (2021) 1386, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13091386>.
- [68] J.Y. Im, B.S. Kim, H.G. Choi, S.M. Cho, Effect of pressure for direct fuel cells using DME-based fuels, *J. Power Sources* 179 (2008) 301–304, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2007.12.046>.
- [69] Q. Li, X. Wen, G. Wu, H.T. Chung, R. Gao, P. Zelenay, High-activity PtRuPd/C catalyst for direct dimethyl ether fuel cells, *Angew. Chem.* 127 (2015) 7634–7638, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.201500454>.
- [70] A.M. Bahmanpour, A. Hoadley, S.H. Mushrif, A. Tanksale, Hydrogenation of carbon monoxide into formaldehyde in liquid media, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 4 (2016) 3970–3977, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.6b00837>.
- [71] A.M. Bahmanpour, A. Hoadley, A. Tanksale, Formaldehyde production via hydrogenation of carbon monoxide in the aqueous phase, *Green Chem.* 17 (2015) 3500–3507, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5gc00599j>.
- [72] J.T. Müller, P.M. Urban, W.F. Hölderich, K.M. Colbow, J. Zhang, D.P. Wilkinson, Electro-oxidation of dimethyl ether in a polymer-electrolyte-membrane fuel cell, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 147 (2000) 4058, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1394018>.
- [73] G. Kéranguéven, C. Coutanceau, E. Sibert, F. Hahn, J.M. Léger, C. Lamy, Mechanism of di(methyl)ether (DME) electrooxidation at platinum electrodes in acid medium, *J. Appl. Electrochem.* 36 (2006) 441–448, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10800-005-9095-6>.
- [74] M.G. Gebru, P. Subramanian, P. Bělský, R.S. Yadav, I. Pitussi, S. Sasi, R. Medlin, J. Minar, P. Švec, H. Kornweitz, A. Schechter, Chemical-dealloying-derived PtPdPb-based multimetallic nanoparticles: dimethyl ether electrocatalysis and fuel cell application, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15 (2023) 56944, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acami.3c11003>.
- [75] L. Schriver-Mazzuoli, J.M. Coanga, A. Schriver, P. Ehrenfreund, Infrared spectra of (CH₃)₂O and (CH₃)₂O + H₂O at low temperature, *Vib. Spectrosc.* 30 (2002) 245–257, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2031\(02\)00045-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2031(02)00045-0).
- [76] V. Gámez, M.L. Senent, M. Carvajal, A. Galano, Competitive gas phase reactions for the production of isomers C₂O₂H₄. Spectroscopic constants of methyl formate, *J. Phys. Chem. A* 123 (2019) 9658–9668, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.9b07270>.
- [77] C. Lamy, A. Lima, V. LeRhun, F. Delime, C. Coutanceau, J.M. Léger, Recent advances in the development of direct alcohol fuel cells (DAFC), *J. Power Sources* 105 (2002) 283–296, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(01\)00954-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(01)00954-5).
- [78] J.A. Schott, C.L. Do-Thanh, W. Shan, N.G. Puskar, S. Dai, S.M. Mahurin, FTIR investigation of the interfacial properties and mechanisms of CO₂ sorption in porous ionic liquids, *Green Chem. Eng.* 2 (2021) 392–401, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GCE.2021.09.003>.